

AN INVESTIGATION OF IN-PLANE PERFORMANCE OF ULTRA-HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITES

Mark K. Hazzard^{1*}, Paul T. Curtis², Lorenzo Iannucci³, Stephen Hallett¹, Richard Trask¹

¹Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol, Queen's Building, Bristol, BS8 1TR, United Kingdom.

Email: mark.hazzard@bristol.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/composites>

²Defence Science and Technology Laboratory, Porton Down, Salisbury SP4 0JQ, United Kingdom.

³Imperial College London, Exhibition Road, London, SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom.

Keywords: Dyneema[®], Laminate, Mechanical Properties.

ABSTRACT

In-plane mechanical properties of an Ultra-High Molecular Weight Polyethylene based Dyneema[®] composite were investigated at low strain rates. Low shear properties dominated the in-plane tensile response of the laminate through the lack of ability to transfer load between fibres, causing the strain state in the gauge region to be non-uniform. Averaged cross-sectional stress therefore underestimates the failure strength of the laminate, and because of this, the effect of laminate consolidation causing brinelling of fibres was unable to be quantified. The variation in strain across the specimen may however explain the difference in laminate stiffness and failure strain values in open literature. At higher strain rates, increased strength and stiffness of the laminate was found as the tensile response becomes more linear. $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile shear testing showed that results were highly non-linear and, as strains become larger, fibre rotation dominates testing results. In shear, higher consolidation pressures led to a small increase in maximum shear strength but had a negligible effect on laminate stiffness. Finally, an increased strain rate increased shear stiffness as well as shear strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) laminated composites are increasingly being utilised in applications where ballistic resistance is a requirement. The main reason for the selection in impact scenarios is for their exceptional specific strength and stiffness [1]. UHMWPE fibres were developed in the 1970's by DSM and were trademarked as Dyneema[®], and are typically supplied as a cross-plyed unidirectional laminate pre-preg in a [0/90/0/90] configuration with a polyurethane based matrix. Several layers of the pre-preg can then be hot-pressed together into a rigid panel; a HB26 Dyneema[®] panel micro-structural architecture can be seen in Figure 1. During hot pressing, pressures ranging from 14-30 MPa have been reported for Dyneema[®] panels in open literature with a temperature of approximately 120°C [2,3]. Processing effects on ballistic performance were investigated by Greenhalgh *et al* [3] which indicated higher pressures may have increased the fibre/matrix interface strength and reduced inter-ply thickness. Delaminations from the impact event were considered to be mode II dominated at low pressures, however became mode I dominated at higher pressures. Russell *et al* [4] showed that the tensile strength of the yarn exceeded that of 0° plies in a laminate by approximately 20%, thought to be caused by hot-press induced brinelling (indentation) of the fibres between layers. Similarly, Levi-Sasson *et al* [5] and Lässig *et al* [2] also showed much lower laminate tensile strength than predicted from yarn strength, however measured strain to failure as well as stiffness values of the composite vary greatly by up to a factor of 2.

Figure 1: Cross section of hot-pressed HB26 [0/90] panels by optical dark field microscopy.

Here, the in-plane tension and in-plane shear performance of a HB26 [0/90]_n laminate has been investigated at low strain rates. Due to the low interlaminar shear strength and stiffness of the material, a custom in-plane tensile test specimen geometry has been adopted from Russell *et al* [4], and the ability to transfer load to the internal plies of the specimen has been explored. A custom dog bone shear specimen was also designed in order to avoid grip slippage, and failure mechanisms have been investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images. The effect of processing pressure on the final mechanical properties of the HB26 laminate was investigated and it was found that the difference in tensile strength and stiffness was negligible. It was found that the variation in failure strain and stiffness reported literature is largely due to non-uniform tensile loading in the gauge region of the specimen due to low shear properties.

2 MANUFACTURE OF THE TEST SPECIMENS

Laminated panels were manufactured through hot pressing of HB26 [0/90/0/90] plies at 120°C at processing pressures of 10 MPa, 20 MPa, and 30 MPa for one hour. The initial cross-ply laminate precursor was cut to size using a HellermannTyton 60 watt hot knife with an R blade. Microstructural observations were performed using SEM before and after hot compression at the three processing pressures. Prior to hot compression the laminate is very fragile and layers are easily separated, shown in Figure 2. The fibres are approximately parallel to one another apart from regions near the edge where damage has occurred due to manual layer separation. It is clear that layers are not entirely uniform and there are regions of varying ply thickness and fibre gaps. After hot pressing at all pressures total laminate thickness was approximately the same and individual ply thickness was estimated to be 68 μm. Fibre cross sectional area remains unchanged however some fibres have altered cross sectional shape. SEM observations after plies were peeled back showed a more uniform surface compared with pre-hot compression. In all cases there were patches of resin coated fibres and patches that were uncoated. Regions of uncoated fibres were likely caused by peeling back the layers as there tended to be an approximately 50% split of resin distributed on the separated surfaces. Brinelling of the fibres is evident at 10 MPa, 20 MPa, and 30 MPa and can be seen in Figure 3. Figure 3b shows that fibre-fibre contact between layers causes this as resin coated areas have dry circular points of contact between fibres. The degree of brinelling also varied across the surface at all pressures, with some regions having no brinelling and others having a large amount causing large shape change to the cross section of the fibre. It is thought that this variation was due to a non-uniform surface prior to hot compression of the layers causing higher pressure on fibres that are more pronounced. Because of this it is difficult to quantify the effect of processing pressure on the amount of brinelling observed.

Figure 2: HB26 as delivered with one layer half removed.

Figure 3: HB26 after hot compression at a) 10 MPa, b) 20 MPa, and c) 30 MPa.

Due to the low shear strength and stiffness of HB26, a custom specimen was used for tensile and shear testing in order to avoid slip [5]. In tension, a modified Russell *et al* [4] specimen geometry was used (Figure 4a) to introduce high axial stresses to the gauge region via bolting through a large end tab region. For the $\pm 45^\circ$ tension shear test a clamped dog-bone specimen could be used due to lower failure loads (Figure 4b). These specimens were waterjet cut using a standard abrasive mixture with a nozzle diameter of 1 mm, following this holes were cut by laser cutting. SEM images show waterjet cutting shears through the fibres accurately at 90° to the cut direction (Figure 5a); however the process does pull out approximately 3-4 fibres (51-68 μm) from the 0° direction parallel to the cut (Figure 5b).

Figure 4: Sketches of specimens of HB26 employed to measure a) the tensile response of the laminate and b) the shear response of the laminate. All dimensions are in mm.

Figure 5: SEM images of waterjet cutting of HB26 0/90 laminate a) through thickness view with 90° fibres coming out of the page and b) top down planar view.

3 TENSILE TESTING

Tensile testing was performed using a screw driven test machine at constant displacement rates and load was measured directly from a calibrated 100 kN load cell within the Instron machine. The specimen geometry was adopted from Russell *et al* [4] and is given in Figure 4a. The gauge region of the specimen is loaded in tension through intra-laminar shear transfer in the large gripping regions, resulting in a final tensile failure of the laminate. The long gripping regions allow for adequate shear transfer and avoid any fibre pull out. All strain data was captured from an Imetrum Video Extensometer and associated software. The data was captured at an angle of 45° to measure axial strain on the front face of the specimen as well as through the thickness. Here, front face describes the 0° external surface ply (x-y plane Figure 6a), and through thickness describes the cross section of alternating 0/90 plies (x-z plane Figure 6a). As seen from SEM images, the through thickness surface is dominated by 90° sheared fibres from the waterjet cutting process (Figure 5a). A 9 point grid was created on each surface in order to capture longitudinal strains, ϵ_x , transverse strains, ϵ_y , and through thickness ϵ_z strains. In total, 6 strain measurements were made in the longitudinal direction, ϵ_{x1-6} , with strain measurement locations depicted in Figure 6b. During testing the specimen failed in the gauge region in tension, shown in Figure 7a and supported by SEM images of fibre failure similar to that seen by Carr [6]. 3 tests were performed at 0.1 mm/s displacement rate at consolidation pressures of 10 MPa, 20 MPa, and 30 MPa and 1 test at each consolidation pressure at 1 mm/s.

Figure 6: 9 point grid used in testing a) Image from testing showing the front 0° ply (x-y plane) as well as the through thickness direction (x-z plane) and b) a schematic of strain calculations made from positional video extensometer tracking.

Figure 7: a) Photo of tensile failure post-test b) SEM of fibre tensile failure from gauge region.

The measured uniaxial response at a consolidation pressure of 30 MPa and 0.1 mm/s displacement rate is shown in Figure 8. There is a large variation in axial strain ϵ_x in the gauge region by up to a factor of 2, indicating a non-uniform stress state. Through thickness axial strains ϵ_{x4-6} are almost identical until the point of failure at approximately 4%, however the front face strains vary with loading. The lowest strain to failure is recorded by ϵ_{x2} at just below 2%. Comparing the three suggests a strain gradient across the front face of the specimen, with the highest strain at the edge of the specimen, ϵ_{x4-6} , and the lowest in the centre, ϵ_{x2} . Comparing ϵ_{x2} and ϵ_{x5} to literature it is clear that this may be the reason for the large variability in quoted laminate stiffness and failure strains for UHMWPE composites tested in this manner, shown in Figure 9. The variation of processing pressure from 10 MPa, to 20 MPa, and 30 MPa had little effect on the response of the composite as shown in Figure 10. Increasing the displacement rate from 0.1 mm/s to 1 mm/s did however increase the stiffness of the material and the response appears more linear until approaching failure. A summary of final strengths from all testing are given in Table 1, and it can be seen that there are some small variations due to processing pressure but average strengths are very similar and within the standard deviation range. At the higher displacement rate, the average strength of the composite was slightly higher at 685 MPa. This is a well-known phenomenon in polymers as there is less time for plastic slip to occur between inter-chain bonds, and primary bonds break at higher stress levels hence increasing linearity and strength [7]. Here, displacement rate cannot be converted accurately to strain rate due to the variation in strain across the gauge region. Furthermore, the specimen geometry strains outside of the gauge region causing further variation of the strain rate in the gauge region. During testing it was noted that final failure seems to occur gradually, and this can be seen in Figure 8 as linearity of the stress-strain curve reduces when approaching maximum tensile strength. After testing, shear pull in at the top and bottom of the large gripping regions is clearly evident, shown in Figure 11. SEM images show the curvature of 90° fibres perpendicular to the loading direction as 0° fibres are pulled in by approximately 0.75 mm in the central region. Further SEM shows the intra-laminar shear of the matrix as it transfers load from one fibre to another in this region. The low stiffness of the polyurethane matrix allows displacement at the edge of the specimen to be non-uniform. Because of this, fibres loaded in tension near the edge of the gauge region of the ply will be highly stressed compared with fibres in the central region, supporting earlier findings that strain is much higher measured through the thickness at the edge of the specimen compared to the centre of the front face (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Uni-axial loading of a 0/90 specimen at 0.1 mm/s produced at 30 MPa consolidation pressure.

Figure 9: Uni-axial loading of a 0/90 specimen compared with literature.

Figure 10: Comparison of stress strain behavior at 10 MPa, 20 MPa, and 30 MPa consolidation pressures at displacements rates of 0.1 mm/s and 1 mm/s.

Displacement Rate [mm/s]	Processing Pressure [MPa]	σ_{xx} Test 1 [MPa]	σ_{xx} Test 2 [MPa]	σ_{xx} Test 3 [MPa]	Average [MPa]	Std Dev [MPa]
0.1	10	692	669	644	668	20
0.1	20	663	644	700	669	23
0.1	30	682	643	701	675	24
1	-	722	674	659	685	27

Table 1: HB26 tensile testing strengths at different manufacturing pressures.

Figure 11: Fibre pull in at the rear of the specimen grips with SEM images highlighting fibre curvature perpendicular to loading and intra-laminar matrix shear.

3.1 Tensile Test Finite Element Analysis

To further understand the mechanism of load transfer in the composite, a static linear elastic finite element analysis was performed using ABAQUS. Perfectly linear elastic material constants were assumed for the alternating 0/90 UD material and are given in Table 2. In plane Young's modulus was estimated using the rule of mixtures assuming an 83% fibre volume fraction with fibre properties and matrix properties from Kromm *et al* [8] and Karthikeyan *et al* [9] respectively. In-plane linear shear properties were approximated from the following shear testing section. A through-thickness mesh size of 0.07 mm was selected so each UD ply has a single element through the thickness. A mesh seed of 0.5 mm was created on all other edges and meshed using the medial axis algorithm using 3D stress reduced integration solid hex elements. Fully fixed boundary conditions were applied to nodes at the edge of clamping holes, and a linearly increasing displacement up to 7 mm was applied to the gauge region to induce loading of the specimen.

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[-]	[-]	[-]
58930	996	996	86.9	86.9	343	0.3	0.3	0.45

Table 2: Linear elastic material constants used in ABAQUS for UD not cross plied HB26.

The deformed specimen is shown in Figure 12 and shows the strain \mathcal{E}_x throughout the specimen. At the end of the tabbed region, fibre pull in is similar to that observed in Figure 11, however the size of pull in from the model is 2 mm, higher than observed experimentally. Strain \mathcal{E}_x is also shown to be highest at the fillet drop off region and there is a variation across the width of the specimen. The model response across the width of the gauge region is compared with experimental results in Figure 13 through a strain ratio $\mathcal{E}_x / \mathcal{E}_{x2}$, where \mathcal{E}_x is the x strain at a location across the specimen width, and \mathcal{E}_{x2} is the strain at the centre of the 0° ply on the front face. A polynomial fit was applied to experimental results in order to estimate the strain variation across the surface. It can be seen that FEA results show a similar strain profile across the front face of the specimen, however axial strains at the edge of the specimen are lower compared with experimental results. This may be caused by the linear approximation of shear properties in the model compared to the actual specimen response being highly non-linear. Not only are the shear properties non-linear, fibre re-alignment and scissoring must also be taken into account in order to accurately capture this phenomenon at large shear deformations (Figure 11). This is also thought to contribute to the larger pull in depth at the rear of the specimen.

Figure 12: ABAQUS linear elastic quarter model of the tensile response of 0/90 HB26.

Figure 13: Front face strain ratio at the line of symmetry comparing the outer strain to inner strain of the 0° surface ply $\epsilon_x / \epsilon_{x2}$ over the half width of the specimen.

4 SHEAR TESTING

Shear testing was performed on a hydraulically driven testing machine with hydraulic clamping at the grips with a clamping pressure of 4 MPa. Load was measured directly from a calibrated 25 kN load cell and strain data was captured from an Imetrum Video Extensometer and associated software from the front surface of the specimen. Shear strain and shear stress was calculated following ASTM D3518 [10]. A displacement rate of 0.15 mm/s and 1.5 mm/s were used which correlated well to strain rates of 10^{-3} s^{-1} and 10^{-2} s^{-1} respectively. All specimens had the geometry given in Figure 4b and were produced at 10 MPa, 20 MPa and 30 MPa consolidation pressures.

All specimens failed in a classical shear manner in the gauge region, shown in Figure 14a. Also observed was that shear failure was not confined to a particular cross section but actually spread for a length up to 50mm in the gauge region. This was attributed to large delaminations in the cross section when $\gamma_{12} > 0.7$ rad where lamina separation becomes prevalent. The response compared with literature is given in Figure 15. At a strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} the response is almost identical to Lässig *et al* [2] who also did a $\pm 45^\circ$ tension test. It can be seen that the response is highly non-linear. In the initial response, when $\gamma_{12} < 0.2$ rad, the matrix behaviour of the composite is dominant. In this range the response is very similar to Levi-Sasson *et al* [5] who used a butterfly specimen. Assuming linear shear stiffness up to $\gamma_{12} = 0.001$ rad, the average initial stiffness at a strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} for all processing pressures was $G_{12} = 86.9 \pm 9.3$ MPa. When $\gamma_{12} > 0.2$ fibre re-orientation becomes increasingly dominant, and when $\gamma_{12} > 0.7$ delaminations and through thickness expansion occur. The amount of fibre scissoring can be

seen in Figure 14b where $\theta = 65^\circ$ at failure, although the final angle at failure is thought to be much smaller as spring back occurs post-failure. Increased processing pressure seemed to cause an increase in final shear strength from 16.5 MPa to 19.3 MPa at 10 MPa and 30 MPa consolidation pressures respectively, with average shear strengths given in Table 3. The increase in strain rate to 10^{-2} s^{-1} increased stiffness as well as strength, with the initial stiffness rising to $G_{12} = 132 \pm 9.6 \text{ MPa}$.

Figure 14: a) failed shear specimen and b) SEM image of failed shear region showing scissoring between fibres.

Figure 15: The $\pm 45^\circ$ shear response of a HB26 laminate at processing pressures of 10 MPa, 20 MPa, and 30 MPa at strain rates of 10^{-3} s^{-1} and 10^{-2} s^{-1} .

Displacement Rate [mm/s]	Processing Pressure [MPa]	τ_{12} Test 1 [MPa]	τ_{12} Test 2 [MPa]	τ_{12} Test 3 [MPa]	Average [MPa]	Std Dev [MPa]
0.15	10	16.2	17.1	16.3	16.5	0.4
0.15	20	19.0	17.1	16.7	17.6	1.0
0.15	30	19.7	18.6	18.6	19.3	0.5

Table 3: Failure shear strengths at processing pressures of 10 MPa, 20 MPa, and 30 MPa at a strain rates of 10^{-3} s^{-1} .

5 CONCLUSION

In-plane tensile testing of custom dog bone specimens of UHMPWE composites has shown a variation in measured strain in the composite gauge region. In tension the lack of ability to transfer load through a low shear strength and stiffness matrix has meant that higher strain values are seen at the edge of the specimen compared with the centre of the ply. This mechanism was confirmed with a linear FEA analysis, and findings suggest that intra-laminar slip may be the cause of the variability in quoted strain to failure and stiffness values for the UHMPWE composite laminates. Due to the higher loading of edge fibres, stress averaged across the gauge region is considerably lower than that expected at yarn level in this region. Because of this, it was difficult to determine the effect of fibre brinelling on the tensile strength of the laminate at different consolidation pressures. At a higher displacement rate, the laminate tensile response increased in linearity until approaching failure. $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile shear testing showed that results were highly non-linear and as strains become larger fibre rotation dominated testing results. Higher consolidation pressures led to a small increase in maximum shear strength but had no effect on laminate stiffness. An increase in strain rate resulted in an increase in shear stiffness as well as strength as seen previously in literature. In general, testing of the UHMPWE fibre composites was dominated by low shear properties that can even dictate tensile testing results. In the future this data will be used in explicit FEA analyses in order to study a dynamic impact event. This model will be used to understand key impact performance drivers, followed by optimisation of the laminate fibre architecture to reduce areal weight for a given impact velocity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the EPSRC and Dstl for funding this research, and DSM Dyneema[®], in particular Harm Van Der Werff, for supplying the HB26 laminate pre-preg.

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